

Electric Power Network Readiness for EV Charging Rollout in Nairobi

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Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
AMI	Advanced Metering Infrastructure
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
BRT	Bus Rapid Transit
CBD	Central Business District
DC	Direct Current
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EMS	Energy Management System
EPRA	Energy and Petroleum Regulatory Authority (Kenya)
EV	Electric Vehicle
GWh	Gigawatt-hour
HV	High Voltage
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
ITDP	Institute for Transportation and Development Policy
kV	kilovolt
kVA	kilovolt-ampere
kW	kilowatt
kWh	kilowatt-hour
KNH	Kenyatta National Hospital
KPLC	Kenya Power and Lighting Company
LV	Low Voltage
MRTS	Mass Rapid Transit System

MV	Medium Voltage
NaMATA	Nairobi Metropolitan Area Transport Authority
NMA	Nairobi Metropolitan Area
OLTC	On-Load Tap Changer
PCC	Point of Common Coupling
PF	Power Factor
PQ	Power Quality
PSV	Public Service Vehicle
RMU	Ring Main Unit
ROI	Return on Investment
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
THD	Total Harmonic Distortion

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Nairobi is Kenya's primary urban transport market and is expected to be the first large-scale test case for integrating electric mobility into a live distribution network. Kenya's EV registrations increased sharply from 5,294 (2024) to 24,754 (2025), with electric motorcycles accounting for 94.3% of the registered fleet. While motorcycles dominate by volume, the report highlights that buses and minibuses have higher electricity demand due to their higher daily energy use. Total EV electricity consumption reached about 9.1 GWh in 2025, with motorcycles contributing approximately 4.8 GWh (54%) and buses/minibuses about 3.7 GWh (41%), underscoring the need for mixed-use charging hubs that can serve both high-throughput two-wheelers and energy-intensive buses.

The study evaluates Nairobi's grid readiness for commercial charging hub rollout by (i) identifying potential hub locations, (ii) assessing feeder capacity and transformer headroom at priority sites, and (iii) recommending network reinforcement measures. A screening framework was applied to select candidate hubs based on grid proximity and headroom, land availability, investment viability, traffic density, and accessibility for multiple EV classes. The report also contextualizes hub placement using Nairobi's BRT planning especially BRT Line 2 along Thika Road and passenger concentration points, aligning charging infrastructure with real transport demand.

Technically, the grid readiness assessment is anchored on a standard 11 kV feeder design assumption representative of Nairobi's medium-voltage network: 5.5 MVA (5,500 kVA) feeder peak capacity, derived from typical conductor thermal limits. To maintain reliability and operational flexibility, a 10% reserve margin is applied, yielding a planning cap of 4,950 kVA. Charger demand is modelled using apparent power (kVA) with a power factor of 0.95, and a fixed 100 kVA auxiliary allowance is included per depot for lighting, control systems, communications, and ventilation. A feeder-safe mixed-load condition is then used to determine the maximum feasible integer combination of bus chargers and two-wheeler chargers per site, at the feeder peak hour which is the worst-case.

Six sites were assessed and sized as mixed-use depots supplied by five substations and their selected feeders. The results show that substantial charging capacity is feasible at multiple locations, but the feasible charger mix varies significantly depending on the underlying feeder base-load profile. The largest mixed-use hub potential is identified at Stima Club (Amani Substation, Feeder AD) due to very low base loading, allowing 15 bus charger units and 575 two-wheeler chargers (with managed bus charging during the feeder peak window). Roysambu Bus Park (Bustani Substation, Feeder BJ) and KNH Bus Park (Duma Substation, Feeder DH) also demonstrate strong capacity for sizeable depots, while Greenpark Bus Park (Duma Substation, Feeder DM) supports a moderate-sized hub suitable for intercity operations. Ngara Bus Park (Eneza Substation, Feeder EE) is feasible but operates closer to the planning cap due to higher underlying base load; it therefore requires tighter operational controls and monitoring.

A key operational conclusion is that managed charging is essential for scalability, particularly for large bus loads because the binding constraint is not annual energy but coincident peak loading at the feeder peak hour. The report therefore recommends deployment packages that combine (i) phased siting on feeders with higher headroom, (ii) depot-level energy management systems to impose enforceable import caps and schedule bus charging away from network peaks, and (iii) targeted reinforcement where EV demand growth outpaces existing capacity. Recommended reinforcement measures for scalable rollout include transformer and LV upgrades at EV depots, MV feeder reinforcement where required, improved voltage and reactive power support, power-quality monitoring and harmonic mitigation, protection coordination reviews, and enhanced digital monitoring (SCADA/telemetry) for high-capacity charging nodes.

Overall, the study concludes that Nairobi's distribution system can support an early phase of commercial EV charging rollout at strategically selected hubs, provided that (a) feeder-safe sizing is used, (b) bus charging is actively scheduled and/or throttled during peak windows, and (c) network reinforcement is planned in parallel for long-term scale-up.

1.0 Introduction

The rollout of electric vehicle (EV) charging infrastructure depends on the pace of EV adoption, and the existing electricity distribution network can absorb new charging loads at strategically located hubs. This study was undertaken to assess the readiness of Nairobi’s power network to support commercial EV charging at selected locations, with particular attention to feeder loading, transformer headroom, and the operational requirements of high-demand transport segments such as buses and electric two-wheelers.

Nairobi is Kenya’s largest urban transport market and the primary concentration point for commuter movement, last mile delivery and early EV adoption. It provides the most immediate case for evaluating grid readiness for charging infrastructure. National EV registration and electricity-consumption trends are therefore used in this section as a market context for the study. They help indicate which vehicle categories are currently driving electricity demand, how charging behavior is split between peak and off-peak periods, and why those patterns matter when assessing the suitability of specific charging hubs in Nairobi.

Figure 1: Annual New Registration of Electric Vehicles in Kenya, 2018 to 2025

EV registrations in Kenya increased sharply from **5,294 in 2024** to **24,754 in 2025**, demonstrating the rapid acceleration of the country’s electric mobility market. **Electric motorcycles accounted for 94.3%** of all registered EVs, highlighting their dominant role in driving adoption. However, despite this strong growth, the expansion of charging infrastructure has not kept pace and remains

a major barrier to wider EV uptake, particularly for **four-wheeler and Buses electric vehicles**, which require more accessible and reliable charging networks.

The purpose of this contextual analysis is not simply to describe growth in Kenya’s EV market, but to establish the demand-side basis for the network assessments presented in the subsequent sections of the report. In particular, the charts and table below help explain why the study focuses on charging hubs that can support a mixed-use charging model, including two-wheeler charging and larger, more energy intensive bus and Minibus charging operations. This context is essential for interpreting the feeder capacity assessments, depot sizing assumptions, and site-specific recommendations that follow.

Figure 2: Cumulative EV Registrations in Kenya by Vehicle Type

Figure 2 presents the cumulative composition of Kenya’s registered EV fleet and provides an important starting point for this study by showing which vehicle categories are most likely to shape charging infrastructure demand. The chart indicates that electric motorcycles account for the majority of registered EVs, representing about 94% of the total fleet by 2025. The growth of EV’s shown in the chart confirms that any commercially viable charging rollout in Nairobi must account for strong demand from the two-wheeler segment, especially in locations serving high daily vehicle turnover, commuter corridors, and delivery activity.

The chart also shows that vehicle volume alone is not sufficient for charging infrastructure

planning. Although buses, minibuses, passenger cars, and tuk-tuks make up a much smaller share of registered EVs, these categories have different charging patterns, larger battery capacities, and different operational requirements. In a grid readiness study, this distinction is important because the infrastructure required for a site serving mainly electric motorcycles is fundamentally different from that required for a site supporting bus charging. Figure 2 helps frame why the study considers both the scale of likely demand and the type of vehicles expected at each charging hub.

Figure 3: Energy Consumption by Vehicle Type, 2024 and 2025

Figure 3 compares energy consumption by vehicle type in 2024 and 2025 and is more directly relevant to the objectives of this study because it links EV growth to actual electricity demand. While the increase in EV registrations demonstrates market momentum, the rise in electricity consumption shows the scale of load that the distribution network may need to serve as charging infrastructure expands. Total EV electricity consumption reached about 9.1 GWh in 2025, with motorcycles contributing the largest share of demand at approximately 4.8 GWh which accounts for 54% of the total EV Electricity demand. This confirms that the two-wheeler segment is already a major source of charging demand and justifies the inclusion of substantial two-wheeler charging capacity in the charging-hub concepts evaluated in this report.

The chart also highlights a second finding that is highly relevant to feeder and transformer planning: buses and minibuses consume a large share of total EV electricity relative to their small

fleet size. Buses consumed 3.7 GWh in 2025, which accounted for about 41% of total EV electricity demand. For this study, that result is especially significant because the proposed Nairobi charging hubs are designed not only around high-volume two-wheeler charging, but also around the future charging needs of electric buses operating on major public transport corridors. The implication is that site readiness cannot be assessed from fleet counts alone; it must be assessed against the likely load profile created by the vehicle mix expected at each location. In this regard, Figure 3 provides the demand rationale for the technical network assessments in Sections 5 and 6.

Vehicle Category	Tariff	Consumption per Vehicle (Kwh)	Tariff % Consumption	Total Energy (Kwh)	%of Total Consumption
Electric Motorcycles	Peak	3,108,049	65%	4,803,186	54%
	Off Peak	1,695,136	35%		
Electric Tuk-Tuks	Peak	152,834	74%	207,516	0.8%
	Off Peak	54,683	26%		
Electric Passenger Cars	Peak	184,259	57%	320,554	3.4%
	Off Peak	136,295	43%		
Electric Buses & Mini Buses	Peak	821,785	22%	3,698,066	41%
	Off Peak	2,876,280	78%		
Electric Other Vehicles	Peak	28,088	58%	48,642	0.6%
	Off Peak	20,555	42%		
	Total	9,077,964		9,077,964	100.00%

Table 1: 2025 Energy Consumption per Vehicle Type

Table 1 deepens the analysis by showing how 2025 electricity consumption is distributed between peak and off-peak periods for each EV category. This is particularly important because network readiness depends not only on annual energy demand, but also on when charging is likely to occur. Charging demand that coincides with existing system peaks can create higher stress on feeders and transformers, while off-peak charging may be easier to accommodate without immediate reinforcement. The table therefore provides an important bridge between national market data and the localized grid-capacity assessments undertaken for the selected hubs.

The table shows that motorcycles and tuk-tuks have a stronger peak-hour charging profile, indicating that their electricity demand is closely tied to daytime operating cycles. This has direct implications for hub design in Nairobi, where high-traffic locations serving two-wheelers may experience strong daytime charging demand and therefore require careful assessment of feeder spare capacity during already-loaded periods. By contrast, buses and minibuses show a predominantly off-peak charging profile, suggesting that depot-based overnight charging can be aligned more easily with lower-load periods on the network. For this study, that finding supports the feasibility of integrating bus charging into selected sites, provided the feeder and transformer headroom remain adequate during the scheduled charging windows.

Overall, Table 1 reinforces charging-hub planning must be differentiated by vehicle category, operating pattern, and likely charging window. Subsequently, site assessments consider both the magnitude of expected charging demand and the temporal profile of that demand when evaluating whether a location can support a scalable EV charging rollout.

2.0 Study Objectives

The overall objective of this study is to evaluate the readiness of Nairobi's electric power network to support the rollout of commercial electric vehicle (EV) charging infrastructure.

Specifically, the study aims to:

- i) Identify potential electric vehicle charging hubs in Nairobi
- ii) Assess electric distribution feeder network capacity at potential EV charging hub locations.
- iii) Recommend grid network reinforcement measures for scalable EV charging rollout.

3.0 Potential Electric Vehicle Charging Hubs in Nairobi

A structured assessment framework was used to identify the potential electric vehicle charging hubs to ensure both technical feasibility and operational viability. Several factors were considered when assessing suitable sites, including grid infrastructure, land availability, investment considerations, traffic density, and accessibility for different categories of EVs.

Table 2 summarizes the key selection criteria and indicators that form the basis for evaluating and prioritizing potential charging hub locations.

Criterion	Description	Indicators
Availability of Grid Infrastructure	Proximity to substations, feeders, and transformers with adequate capacity.	Distance to nearest primary substation, spare secondary transformer capacity
Availability of Adequate Space	Sufficient land/space for charging bays, parking, and waiting areas.	Land size (m ²), compliance with zoning laws, expansion potential.
Investment & Operational Viability	Economic feasibility of hub establishment and operation.	Expected ROI
Traffic Flow & Vehicle Density	Location near high vehicle activity to ensure high utilization rates.	Average daily traffic counts, proximity to bus termini, taxi stages, and major corridors.
Accessibility for Different EV Types	Ability to serve two-wheelers, three-wheelers, passenger cars, and larger fleet vehicles such as buses.	Road access for larger vehicles, design flexibility for different EV types,

Table 2: Selection Matrix for Potential EV Charging Hubs in Nairobi

3.1 BRT System Assessment

The BRT system assessment covered the following two objectives.

- iv) Studying and analyzing commuter concentration points, traffic flows and the ranges of the available electric buses (including for the bus rapid transport (BRT) line 2.
- v) Providing a cost estimate and other resources needed for setting up an EV charging station.

3.2 The Nairobi BRT System

The Nairobi Metropolitan Area Transport Authority (NaMATA) was established to address urban transportation challenges in the Nairobi Metropolitan Area (NMA) by the Government of Kenya, Legal Notice No. 18 of 2017. NaMATA’s mandate is to oversee the development and implementation of an efficient, effective, and integrated public transport system within the Metropolitan Area. The Nairobi Mass Rapid Transit System Harmonization study of 2014 consolidated the mass rapid transit corridors into 5 key BRT lines within the Nairobi Metropolitan area as indicated in Figures 4 and 5.

Figure 4: Proposed BRT Lines

Figure 5: Gazetted MRTS Corridors in Nairobi

1. Line 1: Limuru - Kangemi - CBD - Mombasa Road - Imara Daima - Athi River and Kitengela.
2. Line 2: Rongai - Bomas - Langata Road - CBD - Thika road - Ruiru - Thika and Kenol.
3. Line 3: Tala – Njiru - Dandora - Juja Road -CBD – Ngong Road - Show Ground and Ngong.
4. Line 4 East: Mama Lucy Hospital - Donholm - Jogoo Road - CBD - T Mall – Bomas - Karen
5. Line 5: Ridgeways - Kiambu Road - Balozi (Allsops) – Outer ring road - Imara Daima

NaMATA is implementing a pilot BRT project along Thika Road (Line 2). The proposed project runs along Thika Superhighway from Ruiru town to Kenyatta National Hospital (KNH) via the central business district (CBD), as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 6: Proposed BRT Line 2 Station and Depot Location (NaMATA)

The project scope includes the construction of dedicated BRT lanes (20.2 km) and retrofitting of existing thirteen footbridges to BRT stations. The project also includes the construction of BRT terminals at Kenyatta National Hospital (KNH), Kasarani, and Ruiru. The main depot at Kasarani, shown in Figure 3 and 4, is meant to be the key charging facility for the line 2 corridor bus fleet.

Figure 7: Ongoing Construction of Kasarani Depot for BRT Line 2

3.3 BRT Value Proposition for Passengers

Passengers using the BRT will benefit from significant time savings. The BRT, operating in a segregated right-of-way, will be able to transport people more efficiently than existing public transport services. It will offer a very high quality of service for users and will help to reduce urban congestion. In terms of time spent riding in public transport vehicles, the average benefit for passengers from Thika to downtown is 22 minutes per trip. From Ruiru to downtown the average benefit is 18 minutes. Residents will save many hours each year that they otherwise would have spent sitting in traffic, thereby improving their quality of life. The dedicated lanes will give the BRT system a speed advantage over vehicles operating in congested mixed traffic lanes. A BRT system that offers quicker journeys and provides convenient access to popular destinations can compete with competing modes, including private cars and taxis.

3.4 Commuter Concentration Points Along BRT Line 2

The Institute for Transport and Development Policy (ITDP 2018/19) conducted a city-wide public transport demand assessment to determine public transport demand and mapped the boarding and alighting patterns for the city. The study revealed high demand in the catchment areas of Juja, Ruiru, Kenyatta University (KU), Kahawa Wendani, Githurai, Kasarani, Mwiki, Roysambu, and Zimmerman as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Passenger Concentration Along Thika Road

It was observed that high passenger demand is generated in Githurai which comprises residential neighborhoods. A service plan for the Thika Road BRT Line 2 was developed that guides bus fleet deployment to meet passenger demand. The service plan estimated peak hour (morning hour from 7:00am to 8:00am) volume as 34,000 passengers per hour per direction (pphpd). The study proposed twelve routes along the corridor with direct services to minimize the need for transfers. The fleet requirement for the proposed 12 service groupings is shown in Table 2.

Route Code	Route Name	Length (km)	Max load (pphpd)	Boardings, peak hour (7:00 – 8:00 am)	Boardings, daily	Headway (min)	Fleet size (no reserve)
B145N	Nairobi to Ruiru (Inbound)	24.1	307	929	8,361	3.7	16
B145S	Ruiru to Nairobi (Outbound)	25.6	2,288	3,783	34,047	3.7	17

B17BE	Nairobi to Baba Dogo (Inbound)	17.7	364	675	6,075	1.9	32
B17BW	Baba Dogo to Nairobi (Outbound)	17.3	4,538	6,583	59,247	1.9	32
B237N	Nairobi to Thika Town (Inbound)	44.3	644	1,489	13,401	3.3	29
B237S	Thika Town to Nairobi (Outbound)	43.4	2,560	3,513	31,617	3.3	29
B237eN	Westlands to Thika Town (Inbound)	44.3	1,634	2,386	21,474	2.8	32
B237eS	Thika Town to Westlands (Outbound)	43.4	3,052	3,204	28,836	2.8	31
B237wN	Railways to Thika Town (Inbound)	44.4	2,273	3,097	27,873	3.1	33
B237wS	Thika Town to Railways (Outbound)	44.1	2,741	2,982	26,838	3.1	34
B25E	Nairobi to Lucky Summer (Inbound)	12.6	234	576	5,184	2.7	16
B25W	Lucky Summer to Nairobi (Outbound)	13.2	3,088	3,716	33,444	2.7	18
B42E	Railways to Juja Road (Inbound)	10.9	206	232	2,088	3.1	11
B42W	Juja Road to Railways (Outbound)	10.7	2,683	2,974	26,766	3.1	10
B42aE	Upperhill to Juja Road (Inbound)	12.9	1,998	2,227	20,043	1.5	30
B42aW	Juja Road to Upperhill (Outbound)	12.6	5,449	6,873	61,857	1.5	29
B42bE	Westlands to Juja Road (Inbound)	11.0	203	207	1,863	8.0	6
B42bW	Juja Road to Westlands (Outbound)	11.4	1,051	1,065	9,585	8.0	6

B44GN	Railways to Kahawa/Zimmerman (Inbound)	18.6	437	1,197	10,773	2.0	31
B44GS	Kahawa/Zimmerman to Railways (Outbound)	18.5	4,204	5,269	47,421	2.0	31
B45KE	Railways to Eastern Bypass (Inbound)	23.7	326	976	8,784	5.8	10
B45KW	Eastern Bypass to Railways (Outbound)	23.6	1,452	2,156	19,404	5.8	10
B45KhE	Nairobi to Juja (Inbound)	34.0	693	1,102	9,918	2.6	31
B45KhW	Juja to Nairobi (Outbound)	33.9	3,291	3,625	32,625	2.6	31
Total		596		60,836	547,524		555

Table 3: BRT Line 2 Network Operational Parameters

4.0 Selected Sites for EV Charging Hub Analysis

A preliminary analysis identified six priority locations for the deployment of electric vehicle (EV) charging infrastructure in Nairobi. These sites were chosen based on their strategic importance, availability of grid capacity, land suitability, traffic density, and accessibility for different categories of EVs. Table 3 highlights the profiles of the proposed sites.

Figure 9: Existing EV Charging Stations and Distribution Substations Along Thika Road

Figure 10: Selected Sites Along Thika Road

Site	Strategic Advantage	Key Traffic Flow	Grid/Space Availability
Stima Club	Touching Thika super highway, near KPLC unutilized space at the Stima club	High traffic from, private cars and taxi waiting bay at Ruaraka	Excellent grid access, available KPLC space
Ngara Bus Park	Junction to Thika Rd & Waiyaki Way; links CBD with outskirts	High PSV and private car traffic	Adequate grid & ample space

Greenpark Bus Park	Long-distance bus terminus; connects to Mombasa Rd & Uhuru Highway	Heavy intercity traffic	Large designated space, strong grid nearby
KNH Bus Park	Largest hospital in Kenya; institutional traffic	Staff, patients, PSV, visitors	Adequate grid, adequate space
Roysambu Bus Park	High-density residential and commercial hub along Thika Superhighway	Daily traffic from estates and malls	Adequate grid capacity, ample space
Ruiru Bus Park	Growing commuter town along Thika Superhighway	Commuter vehicles and matatus	Existing grid, good space

Table 4: Profiles of Selected EV Charging Sites

The site screening results indicate that the most promising locations for early EV charging hub deployment in Nairobi are those where transport demand, accessibility, and grid readiness converge. The selected locations demonstrate that viable charging infrastructure can be anchored in a range of urban contexts, provided that the underlying conditions support both technical feasibility and sustained utilisation.

A key implication of the site selection is that charging hub development in Nairobi should be approached as a network planning exercise, rather than as a series of isolated installations. The diversity of the selected sites suggests that an effective charging network will need to serve multiple mobility functions, including urban commuting, institutional access, intercity movement, and public transport operations. This reinforces the need for charging infrastructure planning to align closely with actual transport patterns and the operational characteristics of different EV user groups.

The findings further show that sites with favourable grid proximity and available space offer the strongest near-term opportunity for implementation, as they are likely to reduce connection costs, shorten deployment timelines, and improve project bankability. In this context, the selected sites provide a practical foundation for phased rollout of EV charging infrastructure in Nairobi, while also offering a basis for replication in other high-demand corridors across the city.

5.0 Grid Capacity Assessment and Charging Feasibility Analysis

5.1 Feeder Capacity Input Data and Design Assumptions

	Conductor size [mm ²]	dia. over cond. [mm]	Insulation thickness [mm]	overall dia [mm]	cable mass [kg/km]	DC Resistance at 20 ⁰ C [Ohm/km]	Current rating in duct [Amps]
	50 (Al)	8.15	3.4	56.40	5340	0.641	125
	95 (Al)	11.54	3.4	65.90	7400	0.320	180
6.35/11 kV	185 (Al)	16.10	3.4	76.50	9560	0.164	255
XLPE	300 (Al)	21.45	3.4	88.90	12225	0.100	330
3/c	300 (Cu)	21.45	3.4	88.90	18050	0.060	420

Table 5: Medium Voltage Cable Characteristics (Aberdare Cables)

The feeder capacity assessment in this study is based on the standard technical characteristics of the 11 kV medium-voltage distribution network commonly applied in Kenya. As shown in Figure 8, the reference conductor used for the analysis is an aluminium 300 mm² feeder conductor, with a maximum current carrying capacity of 330 A, consistent with the distribution design parameters typically adopted by Kenya Power and Lighting Company (KPLC) for primary feeders.

Using this conductor specification, the maximum apparent power that can be carried by the feeder was taken as **5.5 MVA (5,500 kVA)**. This value provides the technical basis for estimating feeder loading, available headroom, and the extent to which additional EV charging demand can be accommodated without exceeding normal operating limits.

Accordingly, the feeder peak capacity applied in this study is:

$$S_{max} = 5.5 \text{ MVA} = 5,500 \text{ kVA}$$

This assumption is important because it establishes the upper design threshold against which existing feeder peak demand is compared. By using the feeder's rated capacity as a benchmark, the study is able to determine the remaining capacity available for EV charging infrastructure and to assess the number of electric buses and motorcycles that could be served concurrently under current network conditions.

The use of this design criterion also reflects actual utility practice, since KPLC feeder planning and expansion are guided by conductor size, thermal loading limits, and operational reliability considerations. As a result, the analysis does not only provide a theoretical estimate of charging

potential, but also anchors the assessment within the practical engineering limits of Nairobi's existing distribution system.

5.2 Feeder Operating Constraint and Reserve Margin

To avoid sustained operation of a feeder at its absolute thermal limit, the analysis applies an operational reserve margin of 10%. This reserve is intended to maintain system reliability, accommodate normal fluctuations in demand, and reduce the risk of overloading during peak operating conditions. In practical network planning, feeders are rarely operated continuously at 100% of their theoretical capacity, as doing so would reduce operational flexibility and increase the likelihood of voltage instability, overheating, and service interruptions.

Accordingly, the safe operating capacity of the feeder is defined as:

$$S_{op} = (1 - \alpha)S_{max}$$

Where:

- S_{op} = safe operating feeder capacity
- S_{max} = maximum feeder capacity
- α = reserve margin

Assuming a reserve margin of 10%:

$$\alpha = 0.10$$
$$S_{op} = 0.9 \times 5,500 = 4,950 \text{ kVA}$$

This means that, although the feeder is rated at 5,500 kVA, only 4,950 kVA is treated as the practical upper limit for planning EV charging demand under normal operating conditions.

5.3 EV Charger Technical Characteristics and Load Assumptions

The charging demand assumptions used in this study are based on representative charger ratings for the vehicle categories considered in the analysis, namely electric buses and electric two-wheelers.

For electric buses, the study assumes a 180 kW charger unit, with each unit capable of charging two buses concurrently over a four-hour period. This reflects the operational requirements of high-capacity charging depots intended to support scheduled bus charging cycles.

For electric two-wheelers, a 3 kW charger is assumed, with the capacity to fully charge one battery in approximately 1.5 hours. This rating is consistent with the lower battery capacity and shorter charging duration associated with motorcycles and similar light EVs.

To convert charger demand from real power (kW) to apparent power (kVA), the study assumes a power factor (pf) of 0.95, based on EV charger datasheets. This assumption is necessary because feeder loading is assessed in apparent power terms.

The corresponding apparent power demand is therefore determined as:

$$S = \frac{P}{pf}$$

Where:

- S = apparent power in kVA
- P = charger real power in kW
- pf = power factor

This gives the effective feeder demand contribution of each charger type and allows the charger loads to be integrated into the network capacity assessment.

5.4 Auxiliary Load Allowance for EV Charging Depot Operations

In addition to the charger load itself, an EV charging depot requires a range of supporting electrical services to enable safe and reliable operation. These include lighting, control systems, communications equipment, safety systems, ventilation, and other auxiliary services.

To account for these non-charging electrical demands, the study includes a fixed auxiliary load allowance of:

$$S_{aux} = 100 \text{ kVA}$$

Including this allowance ensures that the feasibility assessment captures total depot demand more realistically, rather than considering charger load in isolation. This is particularly important for larger charging hubs, where operational support systems form an essential part of the overall load profile.

5.5 Feeder-Safe Charging Capacity Condition for Mixed EV Loads

The technical feasibility of an EV charging depot depends on whether the combined demand from bus chargers, two-wheeler chargers, and auxiliary loads can be accommodated within the safe operating capacity of the feeder.

For a depot with:

- N_{bus} = number of bus charger units operating concurrently
- N_{2W} = number of two-wheeler chargers operating concurrently
- S_{bus} = apparent power demand of each bus charger
- S_{2W} = apparent power demand of each two-wheeler charger

the total depot demand must satisfy the following condition:

$$N_{bus}S_{bus} + N_{2W}S_{2W} + S_{aux} \leq S_{depot,max}$$

Where:

- $S_{depot,max}$ = maximum feeder capacity available to the depot after accounting for existing feeder demand and the reserve margin

This equation defines the feeder-safe limit for any combination of bus and motorcycle charging loads. It provides a practical basis for assessing how many chargers can operate simultaneously without exceeding the feeder's available capacity.

Rearranging the equation to solve for the maximum feasible number of two-wheeler chargers, given a selected number of bus chargers, gives:

$$N_{2W} \leq \frac{S_{depot,max} - S_{aux} - N_{bus}S_{bus}}{S_{2W}}$$

Since charger counts must be expressed as whole numbers, the study applies the floor function to determine the highest feasible integer value:

$$N_{2W,max} = \left\lfloor \frac{S_{depot,max} - S_{aux} - N_{bus}S_{bus}}{S_{2W}} \right\rfloor$$

This formulation allows the study to test different charging depot configurations and determine the maximum number of buses and two-wheelers that can be charged concurrently on each selected feeder while remaining within safe operating limits. It therefore provides the analytical basis for comparing site suitability and estimating the charging potential of each selected location under existing grid conditions.

5.6 Summary of Selected Substations and Feeders for EV Hub Analysis

	Substation	Number of Feeders	Selected Feeder
1	Amani	7	AD
2	Bustani	11	BJ
3	Chui	8	CH
4	Duma	12	DM and DH
5	Eneza	13	EE

Table 6: Summary Table for the 5 Substations and Feeders Selected for Analysis

The study assessed 5 Substations and their respective feeders to identify the most suitable locations for EV hub deployment. Since each substation serves multiple feeders with different load profiles, data was collected and reviewed for all relevant feeders before selecting the most appropriate feeder for detailed analysis.

For each substation, the recommended feeder was selected based on the lowest recorded peak load of the proposed EV hub location to the substation. In all cases, the selected site was located less than 1 km from the substation.

The selected feeders were then analyzed to estimate the number of electric buses and electric motorcycles that could be charged concurrently under the existing network conditions.

Table 6 therefore presents a summary of the five substations and selected feeders analysed in this study, together with the corresponding feeder recommended for potential EV hub development.

6.0 Site-Level Feeder Analysis and EV Hub Sizing

6.1 Stima Club EV Charging Hub

The proposed Stima Club EV charging hub is supplied through Feeder AD from Amani Substation. This site was selected for detailed assessment because of its proximity to the substation, relatively low feeder loading, and strong potential to support a mixed-use EV charging hub for both electric buses and two-wheelers.

The analysis for this site assesses the feeder's available capacity, the proposed EV charging mix, and the resulting impact on feeder loading under weekday operating conditions.

6.1.1 Existing Network Configuration

Figure 11 presents the network diagram for the substation and feeder arrangement serving the Stima Club area. The figure illustrates the power supply configuration and identifies the feeder through which the proposed charging hub would be connected.

Table 7 summarizes the loading levels of all feeders at **Amani Substation** and shows the estimated available capacity on each feeder.

Amani Substation - (2 x 23 MVA)				
Feeder Name	Hub/Feeder Peak Load (A)	Peak Loading (MVA)	Feeder Capacity (MVA)	Available Capacity (MVA)
AA	70	1,334	5,7156	4,382
AB	50	0,953	5,7156	4,763
AC	150	2,858	5,7156	2,858
AD	10	0,191	5,7156	5,525
AE	10	0,191	5,7156	5,525
AF	150	2,858	5,7156	2,858
AG	10	0,191	5,7156	5,525

Table 7: Feeder Loading at Amani Substation

Table 7 shows that Feeder AD has one of the lowest peak loading levels among the feeders at Amani Substation, with a peak load of only 0.191 MVA, leaving approximately 5.525 MVA of theoretical spare capacity. This makes it one of the most suitable feeders for accommodating additional EV charging demand. The table therefore provides the basis for selecting Feeder AD for detailed feasibility analysis.

Figure 11: Network Diagram of Amani Substation

6.1.2 Base Load Profile of the Selected Feeder

Figure 12 presents the weekday base load profile for Feeder AD before the introduction of the EV charging hub.

Figure 12: Base Load Profile of Feeder AD on a Weekday

Figure 12 shows that Feeder AD has a very low existing demand profile throughout the day, with the highest base load occurring during the evening peak period. This relatively light loading creates an opportunity to introduce significant EV charging demand while still operating within safe feeder limits. The base load profile is an important input to the charging hub sizing analysis because it determines the amount of spare capacity available during the worst-case loading hour.

6.1.3 Maximum Depot Capacity Available on Feeder AD

At the worst hour of base load, the maximum allowable EV charging depot import is calculated as:

$$S_{\text{base,peak}} = 190.52 \text{ kVA}$$

$$S_{\text{depot,max}} = 4,950 - 190.52 = 4,759.48 \text{ kVA}$$

This value represents the maximum feeder-safe EV charging depot capacity that can be connected to Feeder AD while maintaining the 10% operating reserve margin.

Using:

$$S = \frac{P}{pf}$$

the apparent power demand of each charger type is determined as follows:

Bus charger unit apparent power

$$S_{\text{bus}} = \frac{180}{0.95} = 189.47 \text{ kVA per charger unit}$$

Two-wheeler charger apparent power

$$S_{2W} = \frac{3}{0.95} = 3.158 \text{ kVA per charger}$$

6.1.4 Selected EV Charging Depot Mix

A balanced charging hub configuration was developed for Stima Club to serve both electric buses and two-wheelers, while remaining within the feeder-safe capacity limit.

6.1.4.1 Selected Bus Charging Capacity

The selected concurrent bus charging capacity is:

$$N_{bus} = 15 \text{ bus charger units}$$

This is equivalent to:

- 30 buses charging concurrently, assuming each charger serves 2 buses
- 4-hour charging sessions for buses

The total bus charging apparent power is therefore:

$$S_{bus,total} = 15 \times 189.47 = 2,842.11 \text{ kVA}$$

6.1.4.2 Maximum Two-Wheeler Charging Capacity

Substituting the bus charging load into the feeder feasibility equation:

$$N_{2W,max} = \left\lfloor \frac{4,759.48 - 100 - 2,842.11}{3.158} \right\rfloor$$

$$N_{2W,max} = \left\lfloor \frac{1,817.37}{3.158} \right\rfloor = 575$$

This means the feeder can support a maximum of **575 two-wheeler** chargers operating concurrently, in addition to the selected bus charging load and auxiliary demand.

6.1.4.3 Total Depot Demand at the Selected Maximum

$$S_{depot} = (15 \times 189.47) + (575 \times 3.158) + 100$$

$$S_{depot} = 2,842.11 + 1,815.79 + 100 = 4,757.89 \text{ kVA}$$

This satisfies the feeder-safe operating condition:

$$4,757.89 \text{ kVA} \leq 4,759.48 \text{ kVA}$$

Therefore, the recommended EV charging depot design for Stima Club is:

- 15 EV bus charging units operating concurrently
- 575 two-wheeler chargers operating concurrently
- 100 kVA auxiliary load allowance

The results show that Stima Club can support a relatively large mixed-use charging hub without exceeding the feeder-safe capacity threshold. This makes the site technically attractive for deployment, particularly as a multi-vehicle charging location serving both public transport and light electric mobility.

6.1.5 Feeder Loading with the Proposed EV Charging Hub

The proposed EV charging depot demand is composed of the following:

Two-wheeler charging demand (constant):

$$S_{2W,total} = 575 \times \frac{3}{0.95} = 1,815.79 \text{ kVA}$$

Auxiliary load (constant):

$$S_{aux} = 100 \text{ kVA}$$

Bus charging demand (variable by time block):

$$S_{bus} = N_{bus} \times \frac{180}{0.95} = N_{bus} \times 189.47 \text{ kVA}$$

When **15 bus charging units** are operating, during the periods **00:00–15:00** and **20:00–23:00**, total depot demand is:

$$S_{depot} = (15 \times 189.47) + 1,815.79 + 100 = 4,757.89 \text{ kVA}$$

When **8 bus charging units** are operating during the feeder peak block **16:00–19:00**, total depot demand becomes:

$$S_{depot} = (8 \times 189.47) + 1,815.79 + 100 = 3,431.57 \text{ kVA}$$

6.1.6 Hourly Feeder Loading with the EV Charging Depot

Hour	Base Feeder Loading (kVA)	Depot Loading (kVA)	New Total Feeder Loading (kVA)
00:00	72.40	4,757.89	4,830.29
01:00	66.68	4,757.89	4,824.57
02:00	60.97	4,757.89	4,818.86
03:00	57.16	4,757.89	4,815.05
04:00	60.97	4,757.89	4,818.86
05:00	72.40	4,757.89	4,830.29
06:00	97.17	4,757.89	4,855.06
07:00	108.60	4,757.89	4,866.49
08:00	114.31	4,757.89	4,872.20
09:00	125.74	4,757.89	4,883.63
10:00	120.03	4,757.89	4,877.92
11:00	116.22	4,757.89	4,874.11
12:00	114.31	4,757.89	4,872.20
13:00	116.22	4,757.89	4,874.11
14:00	120.03	4,757.89	4,877.92
15:00	125.74	4,757.89	4,883.63
16:00	131.46	3,431.57	3,563.03
17:00	142.89	3,431.57	3,574.46
18:00	167.66	3,431.57	3,599.23
19:00*	190.52	3,431.57	3,622.09
20:00	184.80	4,757.89	4,942.69
21:00	167.66	4,757.89	4,925.55
22:00	142.89	4,757.89	4,900.78
23:00	97.17	4,757.89	4,855.06

***Base Peak**

Table 8: Hourly Feeder AD Totals (Base Load + EV Charging Depot Load)

The hourly loading results show that the proposed charging depot remains within the feeder-safe operating limit across all hours of the day. Even during the highest loading periods, the total feeder demand does not exceed the allowable threshold of 4,759.48 kVA, provided that bus charging is reduced from 15 units to 8 units during the evening peak block. This demonstrates that the site is technically feasible for EV hub deployment, but also highlights the importance of managed charging to maintain network reliability during peak demand periods.

6.1.7 Summary of Findings for Stima Club

The Stima Club site demonstrates strong technical feasibility for development as a mixed-use EV charging hub. The low existing base load on Feeder AD, combined with the available feeder headroom, allows the site to support both high-capacity bus charging and a substantial two-wheeler charging operation.

The analysis shows that, under the proposed design, the site can accommodate:

- 15 bus charger units serving 30 buses concurrently
- 575 two-wheeler chargers
- 100 kVA of auxiliary demand

However, the analysis also shows that charging operations must be actively managed during peak hours to ensure the feeder remains within safe operating limits. This makes Stima Club a strong candidate for phased EV hub deployment, particularly where smart load management and operational scheduling can be incorporated into hub design.

6.2 Ngara Bus Park EV Charging Hub

The proposed Ngara Bus Park EV charging hub is supplied through Feeder EE (Kirinyaga Road) from Eneza Substation. This site was selected for detailed assessment because of its strategic location near the CBD and major public transport corridors, as well as its ability to support a mixed-use charging hub for buses and two-wheelers. The analysis for this site assesses feeder headroom, the proposed charging mix, and the resulting impact on feeder loading under weekday operating conditions.

6.2.1 Existing Network Configuration

Eneza Substation - (2 x 45 MVA)				
Feeder Name	Hub/Feeder Peak Load (A)	Peak Loading (MVA)	Feeder Capacity (MVA)	Available Capacity (MVA)
EE	146	2,782	5,7156	2,934
EF	60	1,143	5,7156	4,572
EG	280	5,335	5,7156	0,381
EH	90	1,715	5,7156	4,001
EI	85	1,619	5,7156	4,096
EJ	250	4,763	5,7156	0,953
EK	200	3,810	5,7156	1,905
EL	140	2,667	5,7156	3,048
EN	150	2,858	5,7156	2,858
EO	15	0,286	5,7156	5,430
EP	150	2,858	5,7156	2,858
EQ	250	4,763	5,7156	0,953
ER	70	1,334	5,7156	4,382

Table 9: Feeder Loading at Eneza Substation

Table 9 shows that Feeder EE carries a moderate existing load relative to its total feeder capacity, leaving approximately 2.934 MVA of available headroom for additional demand. For the purposes of this study, this available capacity provides the basis for assessing whether

Ngara Bus Park can support a mixed charging hub without exceeding feeder-safe operating limits.

Figure 13: Network Diagram of Eneza Substation

6.2.2 Base Load Profile of the Selected Feeder

Figure 14: Base Load Profile of Feeder EE on a Weekday

Figure 14 shows that Feeder EE has its highest base loading during the daytime and late-afternoon period, with the feeder approaching its peak at 16:00. This means that any proposed charging hub at Ngara must be sized carefully to remain within the feeder-safe threshold during these higher-load hours.

6.2.3 Maximum Depot Capacity Available on Feeder EE

At the worst hour of base load, the maximum allowable EV charging depot import is calculated as:

$$S_{base,peak} = 2,782 \text{ kVA}$$

At the worst (peak) hour of base load, the maximum allowable depot import is:

$$S_{depot,max} = S_{op} - S_{base,peak} = 4,950 - 2,782 = 2,168 \text{ kVA}$$

This value represents the maximum feeder-safe EV charging depot capacity that can be connected to Feeder EE while maintaining the 10% operating reserve margin.

Using:

$$S = \frac{P}{pf}$$

the apparent power demand of each charger type is determined as follows:

Bus charger unit apparent power

$$S_{bus} = \frac{180}{0.95} = 189.47 \text{ kVA per bus – charger unit}$$

2-wheeler charger apparent power

$$S_{2W} = \frac{3}{0.95} = 3.158 \text{ kVA per charger}$$

6.2.4 Selected EV Charging Depot Mix

A balanced charging hub configuration was developed for Ngara Bus Park to serve both electric buses and two-wheelers, while remaining within the feeder-safe capacity limit.

6.2.4.1 Selected Bus Charging Capacity

Given the high base loading of Feeder EE, the feasible bus charging capacity under the feeder-safe constraint is selected as:

$$N_{bus} = 7 \text{ bus charger units}$$

This equates to 14 buses charging concurrently (2 buses per charging unit) at 4 hour bus charging sessions.

The total bus charging apparent power:

$$S_{bus,total} = 7 \times 189.47 = 1,326.29 \text{ kVA}$$

6.2.4.2 Maximum Two-Wheeler Charging Capacity

Substitute into the sizing equation:

$$N_{2W,max} = \left\lfloor \frac{2,168 - 100 - 1,326.29}{3.158} \right\rfloor = \left\lfloor \frac{741.71}{3.158} \right\rfloor = 234$$

This means the feeder can support a maximum of **234 two-wheeler** chargers operating concurrently, in addition to the selected bus charging load and auxiliary demand.

6.2.4.3 Total Depot Demand at the Selected Maximum

$$S_{depot} = (7 \times 189.47) + (234 \times 3.158) + 100S_{depot} = 1,326.29 + 738.97 + 100 \\ = 2,165.26 \text{ kVA}$$

This satisfies the condition of operating below a 10% reserve feeder loading margin:

$$2,165.26 \text{ kVA} \leq 2,168 \text{ kVA}$$

Therefore, the optimal EV charging depot design for Feeder EE is:

- 7 EV bus charging units operating concurrently
- 234 two - wheeler chargers operating concurrently
- 100 kVA auxiliary allowance.

The results show that Ngara Bus Park can support a moderate mixed-use charging hub under the feeder-safe constraint. However, because the feeder already carries a relatively high base load compared with other selected sites, the charging capacity that can be accommodated is more limited and requires tighter sizing discipline.

6.2.5 Feeder Loading with the Proposed EV Charging Hub

The proposed EV charging depot demand is composed of the following:

Two-wheeler charging demand (constant):

$$S_{2W} = 234 \times \frac{3}{0.95} = 738.97 \text{ kVA}$$

Auxiliaries (assumed constant): 100 kVA

$$S_{aux} = 100 \text{ kVA}$$

Bus demand (assumed constant at maxima):

$$S_{bus} = N_{bus} \times \frac{180}{0.95} = N_{bus} \times 189.47 \text{ kVA}$$

When 7 bus charging units are operating, the total depot demand is:

$$S_{bus} = 7 \times 189.47 = 1,326.29 \text{ kVA}$$

Therefore, the constant depot loading at maxima is:

$$S_{depot} = 1,326.29 + 738.97 + 100 = 2,165.26 \text{ kVA}$$

6.2.6 Hourly Feeder Loading with the EV Charging Depot

Hour	Base Feeder Loading (kVA)	Depot Loading (kVA)	New Total Feeder Loading (kVA)
00:00	1467	2165.26	3632.26
01:00	1410	2165.26	3575.26
02:00	1353	2165.26	3518.26
03:00	1334	2165.26	3499.26
04:00	1353	2165.26	3518.26
05:00	1467	2165.26	3632.26
06:00	1658	2165.26	3823.26
07:00	1772	2165.26	3937.26
08:00	1829	2165.26	3994.26
09:00	2362	2165.26	4527.26
10:00	2591	2165.26	4756.26
11:00	2667	2165.26	4832.26
12:00	2763	2165.26	4928.26
13:00	2724	2165.26	4889.26
14:00	2629	2165.26	4794.26
15:00	2724	2165.26	4889.26
16:00*	2782	2165.26	4947.26

17:00	2515	2165.26	4680.26
18:00	2458	2165.26	4623.26
19:00	2382	2165.26	4547.26
20:00	2153	2165.26	4318.26
21:00	1619	2165.26	3784.26
22:00	1448	2165.26	3613.26
23:00	1238	2165.26	3403.26

* Base Peak

Table 10: Hourly Feeder EE Totals (Base Load + EV Charging Depot Load)

6.2.6 Hourly Feeder Loading with the EV Charging Depot

The hourly loading results show that the proposed EV charging depot remains within the feeder-safe operating limit across all hours of the day under the selected charging configuration.

Even during the highest loading periods, the total feeder demand does not exceed the allowable threshold of **4,947 kVA**, provided that bus charging is reduced from **7 units** between 13:00 to 18:00hrs

Although total feeder loading increases significantly following the introduction of the depot load, the combined demand remains below the allowable operating threshold, indicating that the feeder can technically support the proposed mix of bus and two-wheeler charging.

6.2.7 Summary of Findings for Ngara Bus Park

The hourly loading results show that the proposed charging depot remains within the feeder-safe operating limit throughout the day, with the highest combined load reaching 4,947.26 kVA during the feeder peak hour at 16:00hrs. This indicates that the site is technically feasible, but it also operates close to the allowable planning limit and would therefore benefit from active charging management and close operational monitoring.

Ngara Bus Park is technically feasible for EV charging hub development, but it is more constrained than several of the other selected sites.

The analysis shows that, under the proposed design, the site can accommodate:

- 7 bus charger units,
- 234 two-wheeler chargers,
- a 100 kVA auxiliary demand

This makes the site suitable for phased deployment, particularly where operational controls are used to manage charging demand close to the feeder peak.

6.3 Greenpark Bus Park EV Charging Hub

The proposed Greenpark Bus Park EV charging hub is supplied through Feeder DM from Duma Substation. The site is strategically important because of its role as a major intercity and long-distance passenger node, making it well suited for a mixed charging model that includes both electric buses and two-wheelers. The analysis below evaluates feeder capacity, the selected charging mix, and the resulting daily loading profile.

6.3.1 Existing Network Configuration

Table 11 summarizes the loading levels of all feeders at Duma Substation and shows the estimated available capacity on each feeder.

Duma Substation - (2 x 45 MVA)				
Feeder Name	Hub/Feeder Peak Load (A)	Peak Loading (MVA)	Feeder Capacity (MVA)	Available Capacity (MVA)
DD	70	1,334	5,7156	4,382
DE	160	3,048	5,7156	2,667
DF	150	2,858	5,7156	2,858
DG	120	2,286	5,7156	3,429
DH	70	1,334	5,7156	4,382
DI	45	0,857	5,7156	4,858
DK	75	1,429	5,7156	4,287
DL	120	2,286	5,7156	3,429
DM	110	2,096	5,7156	3,620
DN	110	2,096	5,7156	3,620
DO	170	3,239	5,7156	2,477

Table 11: Feeder Loading at Duma Substation

Table 11 shows that Feeder DM has about 3.620 MVA of available capacity at Greenpark, providing sufficient headroom for a sizeable charging hub. This makes the feeder suitable

for detailed analysis, particularly given the strategic importance of Greenpark Bus Park as a major passenger interchange.

Figure 15: Network Diagram of Duma Substation

6.3.2 Base Load Profile of the Selected Feeder

Figure 16 presents the weekday base load profile for Feeder DM before the introduction of the EV charging hub.

Figure 16: Base Load Profile of Feeder DM on a Weekday

Figure 16 shows that Feeder DM has a relatively stable daytime loading profile, with its highest base demand occurring in the evening peak period. This load pattern allows the charging hub to be sized with greater confidence, while still requiring the analysis to test performance at the feeder peak hour.

6.3.3 Maximum Depot Capacity Available on Feeder DM

At the worst hour of base load, the maximum allowable EV charging depot import is calculated as:

$$S_{base,peak} = 2,096 \text{ kVA}$$

At the worst (peak) hour of base load, the maximum allowable depot import is:

$$S_{depot,max} = S_{op} - S_{base,peak} \quad S_{depot,max} = 4,950 - 2,096 = 2,854 \text{ kVA}$$

This value represents the maximum feeder-safe EV charging depot capacity that can be connected to Feeder AD while maintaining the 10% operating reserve margin.

Using:

$$S = \frac{P}{pf}$$

the apparent power demand of each charger type is determined as follows:

EV Bus charging unit apparent power

$$S_{bus} = \frac{180}{0.95} = 189.47 \text{ kVA per bus - charger unit}$$

Two-wheeler charger apparent power

$$S_{2W} = \frac{3}{0.95} = 3.158 \text{ kVA per charger}$$

6.3.4 Selected EV Charging Depot Mix

A balanced charging hub configuration was developed for Greenpark Bus Park to serve both electric buses and two-wheelers, while remaining within the feeder-safe capacity limit.

6.3.4.1 Selected Bus Charging Capacity

For Feeder DM, the selected concurrent bus charging capacity is:

$$N_{bus} = 9 \text{ bus charging units}$$

This is equivalent to:

- 18 buses charging concurrently, assuming each charger serves 2 buses
- 4-hour charging sessions for buses

The total bus charging apparent power is therefore:

$$S_{bus,total} = 9 \times 189.47 = 1,705.23 \text{ kVA}$$

6.3.4.2 Maximum Two-Wheeler Charging Capacity

Substituting the bus charging load into the feeder feasibility equation:

$$N_{2W,max} = \left\lfloor \frac{2,854 - 100 - 1,705.23}{3.158} \right\rfloor = \left\lfloor \frac{1,048.77}{3.158} \right\rfloor = 332$$

6.3.4.3 Total Depot Demand at the Selected Maximum

$$S_{depot} = (9 \times 189.47) + (332 \times 3.158) + 100$$

$$S_{depot} = 1,705.23 + 1,048.46 + 100 = 2,853.69 \text{ kVA}$$

This satisfies the condition of operating below a 10% reserve feeder loading margin:

$$2,853.69 \text{ kVA} \leq 2,854 \text{ kVA}$$

Therefore, the recommended EV charging depot design for Greenpark is:

- 9 bus charger units operating concurrently.

- 332 two-wheeler chargers operating concurrently.
- 100 kVA auxiliary allowance.

The results show that Greenpark Bus Park can support a sizeable mixed-use charging hub while remaining within feeder-safe limits. This is particularly relevant for the site because of its role as a long-distance and intercity transport node, where future charging demand could be operationally concentrated.

6.3.5 Feeder Loading with the Proposed EV Charging Hub

The proposed EV charging depot demand is composed of the following:

Two-wheeler charging demand (constant):

$$S_{2W} = 332 \times \frac{3}{0.95} = 1,048.46 \text{ kVA}$$

Auxiliaries (assumed constant): 100 kVA

$$S_{aux} = 100 \text{ kVA}$$

Bus demand (assumed constant at maxima):

$$S_{bus} = N_{bus} \times \frac{180}{0.95} = N_{bus} \times 189.47 \text{ kVA}$$

When 9 bus charging units are operating continuously, total depot demand is:

With $N_{bus} = 9$:

$$S_{bus} = 9 \times 189.47 = 1,705.23 \text{ kVA}$$

Therefore, the constant depot loading at maxima is:

$$S_{depot} = 1,705.23 + 1,048.46 + 100 = 2,853.69 \text{ kVA}$$

Hour	Base Feeder Loading (kVA)	Depot Loading (kVA)	New Total Feeder Loading (kVA)
00:00	1503	2,853.69	4,356.69
01:00	1475	2,853.69	4,328.69
02:00	1446	2,853.69	4,299.69
03:00	1433	2,853.69	4,286.69
04:00	1446	2,853.69	4,299.69
05:00	1503	2,853.69	4,356.69
06:00	1631	2,853.69	4,484.69
07:00	1686	2,853.69	4,539.69
08:00	1715	2,853.69	4,568.69
09:00	1772	2,853.69	4,625.69
10:00	1743	2,853.69	4,596.69
11:00	1728	2,853.69	4,581.69
12:00	1715	2,853.69	4,568.69
13:00	1728	2,853.69	4,581.69
14:00	1743	2,853.69	4,596.69
15:00	1772	2,853.69	4,625.69
16:00	1799	2,853.69	4,652.69
17:00	1856	2,853.69	4,709.69
18:00	1983	2,853.69	4,836.69
19:00*	2096	2,853.69	4,949.69
20:00	2067	2,853.69	4,920.69
21:00	1983	2,853.69	4,836.69
22:00	1856	2,853.69	4,709.69
23:00	1631	2,853.69	4,484.69

***Base Peak**

Table 12: Hourly Feeder DM Totals (Base Load + EV Charging Depot Load)

6.3.6 Hourly Feeder Loading with the EV Charging Depot

The hourly loading results show that the proposed charging depot remains within the feeder-safe operating limit across all hours of the day. Even during the highest loading periods, the total feeder demand does not exceed the allowable threshold of 2,854 kVA, provided that bus charging is reduced from 9 units during the evening peak block. This demonstrates that the site is technically feasible for EV hub deployment, but also highlights the importance of managed charging to maintain network reliability during peak demand periods.

6.3.7 Summary of Findings for Greenpark Bus Park

Greenpark site demonstrates strong technical feasibility for development as a mixed-use EV charging hub. The low existing base load on Feeder DM, combined with the available feeder headroom, allows the site to support both high-capacity bus charging and a substantial two-wheeler charging operation.

The analysis shows that, under the proposed design, the site can accommodate:

- 9 bus charger units serving 18 buses concurrently
- 332 two-wheeler chargers
- 100 kVA of auxiliary demand

However, the analysis also shows that charging operations must be actively managed during peak hours to ensure the feeder remains within safe operating limits. This makes Greenpark Bus Park a strong candidate for phased EV hub deployment, particularly where smart load management and operational scheduling can be incorporated into hub design.

6.4 Kenyatta National Hospital (KNH) Bus Park EV Charging Hub

The proposed KNH Bus Park EV charging hub is supplied through Feeder DH (KNH) from Duma Substation. The site is strategically important because it serves a major institutional destination with high daily movement of staff, patients, visitors, and public transport vehicles. The assessment below evaluates whether the feeder can support a mixed-use charging hub while maintaining safe operating limits.

6.4.1 Existing Network Configuration

Table 13 summarizes the loading levels of all feeders at Duma Substation and shows the estimated available capacity on each feeder.

Duma Substation - (2 x 45 MVA)				
Feeder Name	Hub/Feeder Peak Load (A)	Peak Loading (MVA)	Feeder Capacity (MVA)	Available Capacity (MVA)
DD	70	1,334	5,7156	4,382
DE	160	3,048	5,7156	2,667
DF	150	2,858	5,7156	2,858
DG	120	2,286	5,7156	3,429
DH	70	1,334	5,7156	4,382
DI	45	0,857	5,7156	4,858
DK	75	1,429	5,7156	4,287
DL	120	2,286	5,7156	3,429
DM	110	2,096	5,7156	3,620
DN	110	2,096	5,7156	3,620
DO	170	3,239	5,7156	2,477

Table 13: Feeder Loading at Duma Substation (KNH Feeder Listing)

Table 13 shows that Feeder DH has about 4.382 MVA of available capacity, indicating stronger headroom than several other feeders considered in the study. This available margin

is important for KNH Bus Park because the site is expected to serve a combination of public transport and institutional charging demand.

Figure 17: Network Diagram of Duma Substation (KNH Configuration)

6.4.2 Base Load Profile of the Selected Feeder

Figure 18 presents the weekday base load profile for Feeder DH before the introduction of the EV charging hub.

Figure 18: Base Load Profile of Feeder DH on a Weekday

Figure 18 shows that Feeder DH remains relatively lightly loaded throughout the day, with the highest base demand occurring during the evening peak period. This load profile

supports the feasibility of adding significant EV charging demand at KNH Bus Park while maintaining a reserve operating margin.

6.4.3 Maximum Depot Capacity Available on Feeder DH

At the worst hour of base load, the maximum allowable EV charging depot import is calculated as:

$$S_{base,peak} = 1,334 \text{ kVA}$$

$$S_{depot,max} = S_{op} - S_{base,peak} \quad S_{depot,max} = 4,950 - 1,334 = 3,616 \text{ kVA}$$

This value represents the maximum feeder-safe EV charging depot capacity that can be connected to Feeder AD while maintaining the 10% operating reserve margin.

Using:

$$S = \frac{P}{pf}$$

the apparent power demand of each charger type is determined as follows:

Bus charger unit apparent power

$$S_{bus} = \frac{180}{0.95} = 189.47 \text{ kVA per bus - charger unit}$$

2-wheeler charger apparent power

$$S_{2W} = \frac{3}{0.95} = 3.158 \text{ kVA per charger}$$

6.4.4 Selected EV Charging Depot Mix

A balanced charging hub configuration was developed for KNH Bus Park to serve both electric buses and two-wheelers, while remaining within the feeder-safe capacity limit.

6.4.4.1 Selected Bus Charging Capacity

The selected concurrent bus charging capacity is:

$$N_{bus} = 11 \text{ bus charger units}$$

This is equivalent to:

- 22 buses charging concurrently, assuming each charger serves 2 buses
- 4-hour charging sessions for buses

The total bus charging apparent power is therefore:

$$S_{bus,total} = 11 \times 189.47 = 2,084.17 \text{ kVA}$$

6.4.4.2 Maximum Two-Wheeler Charging Capacity

Substituting the bus charging load into the feeder feasibility equation:

$$N_{2W,max} = \left\lfloor \frac{3,616 - 100 - 2,084.17}{3.158} \right\rfloor = \left\lfloor \frac{1,431.83}{3.158} \right\rfloor = 453$$

This means the feeder can support a maximum of **453 two-wheeler** chargers operating concurrently, in addition to the selected bus charging load and auxiliary demand.

6.4.4.3 Total Depot Demand at the Selected Maximum

$$\begin{aligned} S_{depot} &= (11 \times 189.47) + (453 \times 3.158) + 100S_{depot} \\ &= 2,084.17 + 1,430.57 + 100 = 3,614.74 \text{ kVA} \end{aligned}$$

This satisfies the condition of operating below a 10% reserve feeder loading margin:

$$3,614.74 \text{ kVA} \leq 3,616 \text{ kVA}$$

Therefore, the recommended EV charging depot design for KNH Bus Park is:

- 11 EV bus charging units operating concurrently
- 453 two-wheeler chargers operating concurrently
- 100 kVA auxiliary load allowance

The results show that KNH Bus Park can support a relatively large mixed-use charging hub while remaining feeder-safe even at the base peak hour. This makes the

site technically attractive for deployment, particularly because of its strategic role in serving institutional traffic and high daily public transport activity.

6.4.5 Feeder Loading with the Proposed EV Charging Hub

The proposed EV charging depot demand is composed of the following:

The proposed EV charging depot demand is composed of the following:

Two-wheeler charging demand (constant):

$$S_{2W} = 453 \times \frac{3}{0.95} = 1,430.57 \text{ kVA}$$

Auxiliaries (assumed constant): 100 kVA

$$S_{aux} = 100 \text{ kVA}$$

Bus demand (assumed constant at maxima):

$$S_{bus} = N_{bus} \times \frac{180}{0.95} = N_{bus} \times 189.47 \text{ kVA}$$

When 11 bus charging units are operating continuously, total depot demand is:

With $N_{bus} = 11$:

$$S_{bus} = 11 \times 189.47 = 2,084.17 \text{ kVA}$$

Therefore, the constant depot loading at maxima is:

$$S_{depot} = 2,084.17 + 1,430.57 + 100 = 3,614.74 \text{ kVA}$$

6.4.6 Hourly Feeder Loading with the EV Charging Depot

Hour	Base Feeder Loading (kVA)	Depot Loading (kVA)	New Total Feeder Loading (kVA)
00:00	918	3,614.74	4,532.74
01:00	899	3,614.74	4,513.74
02:00	878	3,614.74	4,492.74
03:00	869	3,614.74	4,483.74
04:00	878	3,614.74	4,492.74
05:00	918	3,614.74	4,532.74
06:00	1,008	3,614.74	4,622.74
07:00	1,048	3,614.74	4,662.74
08:00	1,067	3,614.74	4,681.74
09:00	1,107	3,614.74	4,721.74
10:00	1,086	3,614.74	4,700.74
11:00	1,076	3,614.74	4,690.74
12:00	1,067	3,614.74	4,681.74
13:00	1,076	3,614.74	4,690.74
14:00	1,086	3,614.74	4,700.74
15:00	1,107	3,614.74	4,721.74
16:00	1,126	3,614.74	4,740.74
17:00	1,166	3,614.74	4,780.74
18:00	1,256	3,614.74	4,870.74
19:00*	1,334	3,614.74	4,948.74
20:00	1,315	3,614.74	4,929.74
21:00	1,256	3,614.74	4,870.74
22:00	1,166	3,614.74	4,780.74
23:00	1,008	3,614.74	4,622.74

*Base Peak

Table 14: Hourly Feeder DH Totals (Base Load + EV Charging Depot Load)

The hourly results show that the combined feeder and depot load remains within the feeder-safe threshold across the full day, with the highest total load reaching 4,948.74 kVA. This confirms that the selected charging configuration is technically feasible under current network conditions and can be accommodated without exceeding the planning limit.

6.4.7 Summary of Findings for KNH Bus Park

The KNH site demonstrates strong technical feasibility for development as a mixed-use EV charging hub. The low existing base load on Feeder DH, combined with the available feeder headroom, allows the site to support both high-capacity bus charging and a substantial two-wheeler charging operation. KNH Bus Park is one of the stronger candidate sites in the study.

The analysis shows that, under the proposed design, the site can accommodate:

- 11 bus charger units, serving 22 buses concurrently
- 453 two-wheeler chargers,
- 100 kVA auxiliary load allowance while remaining within feeder-safe limits.

The site therefore offers a strong opportunity for a mixed-use charging hub that can serve both institutional and public transport demand.

6.5 Roysambu Bus Park EV Charging Hub

The proposed Roysambu Bus Park EV charging hub is supplied through Feeder BJ (Nakumatt) from Bustani Substation. This location sits within a high-demand commuter and commercial corridor along Thika Superhighway and is therefore well positioned to support substantial charging demand from both buses and two-wheelers. The analysis below examines feeder capacity, selected charger sizing, and the resulting impact on the daily feeder load profile.

6.5.1 Existing Network Configuration

Table 15 summarizes the loading levels of all feeders at **Bustani Substation** and shows the estimated available capacity on each feeder.

Bustani Substation - (2 x 23 MVA)				
Feeder Name	Hub/Feeder Peak Load (A)	Peak Loading (MVA)	Feeder Capacity (MVA)	Available Capacity (MVA)
BB	250	4,763	5,7156	0,953
BC	10	0,191	5,7156	5,525
BD	90	1,715	5,7156	4,001
BE	90	1,715	5,7156	4,001
BF	250	4,763	5,7156	0,953
BG	300	5,716	5,7156	0,000
BH	300	5,716	5,7156	0,000
BI	170	3,239	5,7156	2,477
BJ	55	1,048	5,7156	4,668
BK	150	2,858	5,7156	2,858
BL	150	2,858	5,7156	2,858

Table 15: Feeder Loading at Bustani Substation

Table 15 shows that Feeder BJ has about 4.668 MVA of available capacity, making it one of the stronger candidate feeders within Bustani Substation for EV charging hub

development. This provides a sound basis for assessing Roysambu Bus Park as a high-demand commuter charging location.

Figure 19: Network Diagram of Bustani Substation

6.5.2 Base Load Profile of the Selected Feeder

Figure 20 presents the weekday base load profile for Feeder BJ before the introduction of the EV charging hub.

Figure 20: Base Load Profile of Feeder BJ on a Weekday

Figure 20 shows that Feeder BJ has a comparatively low daytime base load and a sharper rise during the evening period, peaking at 19:00. This loading pattern supports the development of a sizeable charging hub, provided the total depot demand is kept within the feeder-safe limit during the evening peak.

6.5.3 Maximum Depot Capacity Available on Feeder BJ

At the worst hour of base load, the maximum allowable EV charging depot import is calculated as:

$$S_{base,peak} = 1,048 \text{ kVA}$$

$$S_{depot,max} = S_{op} - S_{base,peak} = 4,950 - 1,048 = 3,902 \text{ kVA}$$

This value represents the maximum feeder-safe EV charging depot capacity that can be connected to Feeder AD while maintaining the 10% operating reserve margin.

Using:

$$S = \frac{P}{pf}$$

the apparent power demand of each charger type is determined as follows:

Bus charging unit apparent power

$$S_{bus} = \frac{180}{0.95} = 189.47 \text{ kVA per bus - charger unit}$$

2-wheeler charger apparent power

$$S_{2w} = \frac{3}{0.95} = 3.158 \text{ kVA per charger}$$

6.5.4 Selected EV Charging Depot Mix

A balanced charging hub configuration was developed for Roysambu Bus Park to serve both electric buses and two-wheelers, while remaining within the feeder-safe capacity limit.

6.5.4.1 Selected Bus Charging Capacity

For Feeder BJ, the selected concurrent bus charging capacity is:

$$N_{bus} = 12 \text{ bus charger units}$$

This is equivalent to:

- 24 buses charging concurrently, assuming each charger serves 2 buses
- 4-hour charging sessions for buses

The total bus charging apparent power is therefore:

$$S_{bus,total} = 12 \times 189.47 = 2,273.64 \text{ kVA}$$

6.5.4.2 Maximum Two-Wheeler Charging Capacity

Substituting the bus charging load into the feeder feasibility equation:

$$N_{2W,max} = \left\lfloor \frac{3,902 - 100 - 2,273.64}{3.158} \right\rfloor = \left\lfloor \frac{1,528.36}{3.158} \right\rfloor = 484$$

However, the full depot demand shows that 484 chargers running concurrently makes the depot exceed the 10% cap by approximately 0.11 kVA. Therefore, the feeder-safe integer maximum is taken as:

$$N_{2W} = 483$$

6.5.4.3 Total Depot Demand at the Selected Maximum

$$S_{depot} = (12 \times 189.47) + (483 \times 3.158) + 100$$

$$S_{depot} = 2,273.64 + 1,525.31 + 100 = 3,898.95 \text{ kVA}$$

This satisfies the condition of operating below a 10% reserve feeder loading margin:

$$3,898.95 \text{ kVA} \leq 3,902 \text{ kVA}$$

Therefore, the optimal EV charging depot design for Feeder BJ is:

- a) 12 EV bus charging units operating concurrently
- b) 483 two-wheeler chargers operating concurrently
- c) 100 kVA auxiliary allowance

The results show that Roysambu Bus Park can support a large mixed-use charging hub and remains within feeder-safe limits even after applying the more conservative integer

adjustment from 484 to 483 two-wheeler chargers. This confirms the technical robustness of the selected configuration.

6.5.5 Feeder Loading with the Proposed EV Charging Hub

The proposed EV charging depot demand is composed of the following:

Two-wheeler charging demand (constant):

$$S_{2W} = 483 \times \frac{3}{0.95} = 1,525.31 \text{ kVA}$$

Auxiliaries (assumed constant): 100 kVA

$$S_{aux} = 100 \text{ kVA}$$

EV Bus demand (assumed constant at maxima):

$$S_{bus} = N_{bus} \times \frac{180}{0.95} = N_{bus} \times 189.47 \text{ kVA}$$

With $N_{bus} = 12$:

$$S_{bus} = 12 \times 189.47 = 2,273.64 \text{ kVA}$$

When **12 bus charging units** are operating, the constant depot loading at maxima is:

$$S_{depot} = 2,273.64 + 1,525.31 + 100 = 3,898.95 \text{ kVA}$$

6.5.6 Hourly Feeder Loading with the EV Charging Depot

Hour	Base Feeder Loading (kVA)	Depot Loading (kVA)	New Total Feeder Loading (kVA)
00:00	196	3,898.95	4,094.95
01:00	255	3,898.95	4,153.95
02:00	259	3,898.95	4,157.95
03:00	269	3,898.95	4,167.95
04:00	278	3,898.95	4,176.95

05:00	286	3,898.95	4,184.95
06:00	305	3,898.95	4,203.95
07:00	324	3,898.95	4,222.95
08:00	343	3,898.95	4,241.95
09:00	366	3,898.95	4,264.95
10:00	307	3,898.95	4,205.95
11:00	278	3,898.95	4,176.95
12:00	248	3,898.95	4,146.95
13:00	278	3,898.95	4,176.95
14:00	307	3,898.95	4,205.95
15:00	366	3,898.95	4,264.95
16:00	425	3,898.95	4,323.95
17:00	545	3,898.95	4,443.95
18:00	812	3,898.95	4,710.95
19:00	1,048	3,898.95	4,946.95
20:00	989	3,898.95	4,887.95
21:00	812	3,898.95	4,710.95
22:00	545	3,898.95	4,443.95
23:00	286	3,898.95	4,184.95

***Base Peak**

Table 16: Hourly Feeder BJ Totals (Base Load + EV Charging Depot Load)

The hourly results show that the combined feeder and depot load remains within the feeder-safe threshold across the full day, with the highest total load reaching 4,946.95 kVA. This confirms that the selected charging configuration is technically feasible under current network conditions and can be accommodated without exceeding the planning limit.

6.5.7 Summary of Findings for Roysambu Bus Park

The hourly results show that the total feeder load remains below the feeder-safe threshold throughout the day, reaching a maximum of 4,946.95 kVA at the base peak hour. This

indicates that the site is technically feasible and provides substantial charging potential under current network conditions.

Roysambu Bus Park is one of the most promising sites assessed in this study. Under the proposed design, it can accommodate:

- 12 bus charger units, serving 24 buses concurrently
- 483 two-wheeler chargers,
- 100 kVA auxiliary demand load allowance

Its location on a major commuter corridor and its strong electrical headroom make it a compelling candidate for early deployment.

6.6 Ruiru Bus Park EV Charging Hub

The proposed Ruiru Bus Park EV charging hub is supplied through Feeder CH from Chui Substation. The site is important because it serves a growing commuter town on the Thika corridor and offers a practical opportunity for scaling charging infrastructure outside the city core while still supporting high daily traffic volumes. The analysis below examines available feeder capacity, the proposed charging mix, and the resulting daily loading pattern.

6.6.1 Existing Network Configuration

Table 17 summarizes the loading levels of all feeders at **Chui Substation** and shows the estimated available capacity on each feeder.

Chui Substation - 66/11kV (2 x 23 MVA)				
Feeder Name	Hub/Feeder Peak Load (A)	Peak Loading (MVA)	Feeder Capacity (MVA)	Available Capacity (MVA)
CC	185	3,525	5,7156	2,191
CE	290	5,525	5,7156	0,191
CF	290	5,525	5,7156	0,191
CG	210	4,001	5,7156	1,715
CH	70	1,334	5,7156	4,382
CI	350	6,668	7,6208	0,953
CJ	180	3,429	5,7156	2,286
66/33kV (1 x 23MVA)				
CK	95	5,430	17,1468	11,717

Table 17: Feeder Loading at Chui Substation

Table 17 shows that Feeder CH has about 4.382 MVA of available capacity, indicating that the feeder can accommodate a relatively large additional load under controlled operating conditions. This makes it a practical candidate for evaluating an EV charging hub at Ruiru Bus Park.

Figure 21: Network Diagram of Chui Substation

6.6.2 Base Load Profile of the Selected Feeder

Figure 22 presents the weekday base load profile for Feeder CH before the introduction of the EV charging hub.

Figure 22: Base Load Profile of Feeder CH on a Weekday

Figure 22 shows that Feeder CH has a relatively low daytime loading profile, with demand rising toward the evening peak at 19:00. This profile provides a good technical

basis for integrating additional EV charging demand, provided that the total charging load is kept within the feeder-safe margin.

6.6.3 Maximum Depot Capacity Available on Feeder CH

At the worst hour of base load, the maximum allowable EV charging depot import is calculated as:

$$S_{base,peak} = 1,334 \text{ kVA}$$

$$S_{depot,max} = S_{op} - S_{base,peak} = 4,950 - 1,334 = 3,616 \text{ kVA}$$

This value represents the maximum feeder-safe EV charging depot capacity that can be connected to Feeder AD while maintaining the 10% operating reserve margin.

Using:

$$S = \frac{P}{pf}$$

Bus charger unit apparent power

$$S_{bus} = \frac{180}{0.95} = 189.47 \text{ kVA per bus - charger unit}$$

2-wheeler charger apparent power

$$S_{2W} = \frac{3}{0.95} = 3.158 \text{ kVA per charger}$$

6.6.4 Selected EV Charging Depot Mix

A balanced charging hub configuration was developed for Ruiru Bus Park to serve both **electric buses** and **two-wheelers**, while remaining within the feeder-safe capacity limit.

6.6.4.1 Selected Bus Charging Capacity

For Feeder CH, the selected concurrent bus charging capacity is:

$$N_{bus} = 11 \text{ bus charger units}$$

This is equivalent to:

- 22 buses charging concurrently, assuming each charger serves 2 buses

- 4-hour charging sessions for buses

The total bus charging apparent power is therefore:

$$S_{bus,total} = 11 \times 189.47 = 2,084.17 \text{ kVA}$$

6.6.4.2 Maximum Two-Wheeler Charging Capacity

Substituting the bus charging load into the feeder feasibility equation:

$$N_{2W,max} = \left\lfloor \frac{3,616 - 100 - 2,084.17}{3.158} \right\rfloor = \left\lfloor \frac{1,431.83}{3.158} \right\rfloor = 453$$

Therefore, the feeder CH can support a maximum of **453 two-wheeler** chargers operating concurrently, in addition to the selected bus charging load and auxiliary demand.

6.6.4.3 Total Depot Demand at the Selected Maximum

$$S_{depot} = (11 \times 189.47) + (453 \times 3.158) + 100$$

$$S_{depot} = 2,084.17 + 1,430.57 + 100 = 3,614.74 \text{ kVA}$$

This satisfies the condition of operating below a 10% reserve feeder loading margin:

$$3,614.74 \text{ kVA} \leq 3,616 \text{ kVA}$$

Therefore, the optimal EV charging depot design for Feeder CH is:

- 11 EV bus charging units operating concurrently
- 453 two-wheeler chargers operating concurrently
- 100 kVA auxiliary allowance

The results show that Ruiru Bus Park can support a relatively large mixed-use charging hub while remaining within feeder-safe limits. This is significant because the site demonstrates that strong charging potential is not limited to central Nairobi locations, but can also extend to major commuter towns along the wider corridor.

6.6.5 Feeder Loading with the Proposed EV Charging Hub

The proposed EV charging depot demand is composed of the following:

Two-wheeler charging demand (constant):

$$S_{2W} = 453 \times \frac{3}{0.95} = 1,430.57 \text{ kVA}$$

Auxiliaries (assumed constant): 100 kVA

$$S_{aux} = 100 \text{ kVA}$$

Bus demand (assumed constant at maxima):

$$S_{bus} = N_{bus} \times \frac{180}{0.95} = N_{bus} \times 189.47 \text{ kVA}$$

When 11 bus charging units are operating, the total depot demand is:

With $N_{bus} = 11$:

$$S_{bus} = 11 \times 189.47 = 2,084.17 \text{ kVA}$$

Therefore, the constant depot loading at maxima is:

$$S_{depot} = 2,084.17 + 1,430.57 + 100 = 3,614.74 \text{ kVA}$$

6.6.6 Hourly Feeder Loading with the EV Charging Depot

Hour	Base Feeder Loading (kVA)	Depot Loading (kVA)	New Total Feeder Loading (kVA)
00:00	149	3,614.74	3,763.74
01:00	219	3,614.74	3,833.74
02:00	290	3,614.74	3,904.74
03:00	290	3,614.74	3,904.74
04:00	290	3,614.74	3,904.74
05:00	290	3,614.74	3,904.74
06:00	290	3,614.74	3,904.74
07:00	311	3,614.74	3,925.74
08:00	381	3,614.74	3,995.74
09:00	522	3,614.74	4,136.74
10:00	452	3,614.74	4,066.74
11:00	417	3,614.74	4,031.74

12:00	381	3,614.74	3,995.74
13:00	417	3,614.74	4,031.74
14:00	452	3,614.74	4,066.74
15:00	522	3,614.74	4,136.74
16:00	593	3,614.74	4,207.74
17:00	734	3,614.74	4,348.74
18:00	1,052	3,614.74	4,666.74
19:00*	1,334	3,614.74	4,948.74
20:00	1,263	3,614.74	4,877.74
21:00	1,052	3,614.74	4,666.74
22:00	734	3,614.74	4,348.74
23:00	170	3,614.74	3,784.74

***Base Peak**

Table 18: Hourly Feeder CH Totals (Base Load + EV Charging Depot Load)

The hourly results show that the total feeder load remains within the feeder-safe threshold throughout the day, with the highest combined load reaching 4,948.74 kVA at the base peak hour. This confirms the technical feasibility of the selected charging configuration under existing network conditions.

6.6.7 Summary of Findings for Ruiru Bus Park

Ruiru Bus Park is technically feasible for a medium-to-large EV charging hub under the design assumptions used in this study.

The analysis shows that, under the proposed design, the site can accommodate:

- 11 bus charger units, serving 22 buses concurrently
- 453 two-wheeler chargers.
- 100 kVA auxiliary load allowance while remaining within feeder-safe limits.

This makes it a strong candidate for phased rollout along the Thika corridor.

7.0 Conclusion

The findings of this study show that Nairobi already has a practical foundation for the phased rollout of EV charging infrastructure, provided that deployment is guided by transport demand, feeder capacity, and managed charging principles. The market context presented in Section 1 demonstrates that Kenya’s EV transition is accelerating rapidly, led primarily by electric motorcycles in terms of fleet size and by buses and motorcycles in terms of electricity demand. This confirms that future charging infrastructure in Nairobi must be planned as a mixed-use system capable of serving both high-volume two-wheeler charging and more energy-intensive bus operations.

Number	Site Location	EV Bus Chargers	Electric 2 Wheeler Chargers
1	Stima Club	15	575
2	Ngara Bus Park	7	234
3	Greenpark Bus Park	9	332
4	KNH Bus Park	11	453
5	Roysambu Bus Park	12	483
6	Ruiru Bus Park	11	453
	Total	65	2530

Table 19: Summary of EV Bus Chargers and Electric 2-Wheeler Chargers in 6 Depot Stations

The site-screening analysis in Sections 3 and 4 further shows that viable charging hubs are most likely to emerge where traffic concentration, accessibility, space availability, and proximity to grid infrastructure coincide. The selected sites therefore represent more than isolated land parcels; they form the basis of a potential urban charging network that can serve commuter, institutional, intercity, and corridor-based transport demand. This reinforces the conclusion that EV charging rollout in Nairobi should be approached as a network planning exercise that aligns transport patterns with electrical system capability.

The technical assessment in Sections 5 and 6 confirms that all six selected sites can support EV charging hubs under existing network conditions when feeder-safe design assumptions are applied. Using a feeder operating limit of 4,950 kVA, a 10% reserve margin, representative charger ratings, and a 100 kVA auxiliary load allowance, the analysis demonstrates that each selected feeder can accommodate a feasible mix of bus chargers and two-wheeler chargers while remaining within

safe loading thresholds. However, the extent of feasible charging capacity differs across sites depending on the existing feeder load profile and the amount of available headroom at the feeder peak hour.

Among the sites assessed, Stima Club offers the highest two-wheeler and bus charging potential, reflecting its very low existing feeder load and large spare capacity. Roysambu, KNH, and Ruiru also perform strongly and can support relatively large mixed-use charging hubs under current conditions. Greenpark and Ngara remain technically feasible, but their lower available headroom means that charger sizing must be more carefully constrained. In practical terms, this indicates that Nairobi can begin with a phased rollout strategy that prioritises technically stronger locations while still planning for future reinforcement or managed charging at more constrained sites.

A key conclusion from the hourly loading analysis is that feeder adequacy alone is not sufficient; operational charging control will also be essential. Several sites operate close to the feeder-safe threshold during peak hours, showing that smart charging, load management, and careful scheduling will be critical to maintaining system reliability as utilisation grows. This is particularly important for sites expected to serve buses, where charging demand is concentrated and power intensive. Accordingly, the study supports a deployment model in which charging hubs are introduced in phases, monitored closely, and integrated with operational controls from the outset.

Overall, the study concludes that Nairobi's distribution network is sufficiently ready to support the initial rollout of commercial EV charging hubs at the selected locations, without immediate large-scale network reinforcement at every site. The strongest near-term opportunity lies in deploying charging infrastructure where transport demand and spare feeder capacity already align, while using managed charging and targeted network upgrades to unlock additional capacity over time. This provides a credible pathway for scaling EV charging infrastructure in Nairobi in a manner that is technically feasible, operationally reliable, and aligned with the city's evolving mobility transition.

8.0 Recommendations

1. Policy updates to require depot charging stations to have EMS controls, import caps (kW/kVA) at the PCC, telemetry, and the ability to sequence chargers to stay within feeder limits. This will reduce reinforcement cost and will speed EV charging infrastructure roll-out.
2. Use smart charging, time-of-use tariffs, and demand response technologies to shave peak demand, buffer fast charging, and defer network upgrades.
3. Upgrade distribution transformers and LV mains which are often the binding constraint in the to allow the flexibility of installing EV charging stations for individual use. Consider building dedicated feeders for large EV depots where demand is sustained.
4. Employ Smart Metering Technology - Digitize operations to make scaling repeatable.